

TELOMERASE-INHIBITION AS ANTI-CANCER THERAPY: CURRENT ADVANCES & FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: Telomeres are the defensive structure at the end of chromosomes that helps in maintaining genomic integrity but are progressively shortened due to successive cell division. This phenomenon leads to senescence or apoptosis that is the safeguarding check point mechanism of a cell against any malfunctioning. However, ribonucleoprotein telomerase maintains them in various cancer cells, leading to tumour proliferation. The identification of components of telomerase holoenzyme and the protein subunits attached to telomeres has been made in the past, where proteins play a significant role in the mechanisms of telomere length regulation. Advanced technologies have identified various new anti-cancer strategies to target telomerase and its allied proteins to prevent cancer cell proliferation. Following our growing knowledge on the subject, this review is aimed to covers in-depth description of the recent advances in telomerase research, structure of telomere and the details of proteins associated with it along with those of telomerase, which are integral in telomere length maintenance. This review also summarizes anti-telomerase cancer therapeutic approaches, i.e., inhibition of telomerase activity, ranging from potential targets to synthetic chemical compounds to natural phytochemicals. Thus, the review highlights the importance of considering telomerase as a potential anti-cancer target.

Index Terms - Telomerase, Cancer, DNA-damage, Ageing, Senescence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a genetic disorder in which cells with accumulated errors undergo uncontrolled growth, i.e., acquire the capability of replicative immortality (1). Normal cells could only replicate a certain number of times until they cease dividing (replicative senescence) (2, 3). This is evident from several substantial experiments in which fibroblasts divide for 50 cycles in a culture (4, 5). This shows that cellular aging depends upon many cell divisions per gene but not on time (3, 6–8). Thus, an intrinsic molecular counting process results in replicative senescence. Normal cell chromosomes' ends have long stretched repetitive sequence 5'-TTAGGG-3', and with each cell division, about 150-200 base pairs are lost due to the complete replication challenge. Cells appear in an irrevocable maturation arrest phase (**Figure 1.**) when their telomeres get too short, resulting in senescence (9). Telomerase, a eukaryotic (true nucleus) ribonucleoprotein complex, stabilizes genomic ends by synthesizing the 3' ends of linear chromosomes (10), inhibiting DNA losses by reverse transcriptase activation. Although telomerase activity is often inactive in normal germ cells (9, 11, 12), (Figure 2), it is functional throughout fetal development (13, 14). It tends to stay inactive with various proliferative cells, including stem cells, activated lymphocytes, and hair follicles (15). A significantly suppressed phase of telomerase occurs but remains traceable in many adult cells, including epithelial, fibroblasts, endothelium, and others. Besides

escaping mortality by increased telomerase activity, an alternative (ALT) mechanism also maintains telomeres, thus avoiding senescence. It provides telomere length maintenance by telomerase, allowing the long-term proliferation of tumor cells in cancer (2, 11, 12, 16–19). Then, the discussion will highlight the variety of methods by which telomerase can be inhibited to avoid cancer cell proliferation. However, in cancer cells telomere shortening is absent therefore cells do not undergo the stages that are generally experienced by normal cells as mentioned above (*Figure 2*).

TELOMERE SHORTENING LEADS TO REPLICATIVE SENESCENCE

Telomeres are structures protecting chromosomal ends, containing repetitive DNA sequences and associated proteins. As per the carcinogenesis approach, telomeres in human germ cells were significantly reduced among each cellular division (9, 12, 16, 17, 19, 20). After around 50 to 60 cell cycles, telomeres of some cells are considerably short to induce DNA damage response (DDR) due to chromosomal instability and p53 activation, thus causing replicative senescence (*Figure 3*). Shreds of evidence from various studies elucidate the relation between the shortening of telomere and proliferative failure of cells.

When derived from a young person, human fibroblasts are seen to have longer. A marked probe, specifically for TTAGGG telomeres, was used for in situ hybridization where telomeres run with solid signals. Patients with sudden overaged syndromes such as Hutchinson-Guilford disorder, Werner's disorder, and Trisomy 21 have shortened telomeres than maturity level controls, and cells are procured from these patients that have reduced pluripotency in culture (9). However, some cells can acquire genetic mutations in p53 or other checkpoint proteins (17) and hence overcome early maturation and persist in proliferating (long life expectancy span) until substantial critically compressed telomeres. Therefore, replicative maturation and crisis are two critically essential deterrents preventing cell immortalization and ultimate malignancy. The former (mortality stage 1, M1) includes inhibition of cellular proliferation. Cancer induced alterations bypass M1, allowing for a longer lifespan as telomeres significantly shrink, resulting in a novel abnormal state known as a crisis (M2), including total clonal expansion aging, end-to-end chromosomal fusions, and substantial apoptosis (10). The Breakage-Fusion-Bridge Cycle (BFB) occurs in the ana-phase due to telomere degradation, chromatid chromosome development, and physio-mechanical mitotic spindle load. In the BFB cycle, the production of pair of chromosomes deficient sufficient telomeres at both terminal ends could result in any further chromosomal duplication, deletion, inversion, and translocation (21, 22), also ref (*Figure 4*).

This causes extensive cell death. At this point, specific rare cells activate telomerase (or ALT pathway) to acquire immortality and proceed to carcinogenesis (17). These cells maintain a stable condition, but the telomere length is compressed to allow for continual cell development, subsequently leading to the growth of malignant tumour cells (*Figure 2*). This is accomplished by increasing telomerase expression, which is encoded by the human Telomerase reverse transcriptase (hTERT) gene. Telomerase is a ribonucleoprotein complex with reverse transcriptase activity and a functional RNA coded by hTR, as previously stated (hTERC), Ref (*Figure 5*). Although the hTERT gene is ordinarily silent in approximately all somatic cells, it is expressed strongly in 90% of human malignancies (10, 17).

TELOMERE, TELOMERASE AND THEIR ASSOCIATED PROTEINS

Telomeres are preventive capping structures composed of a differing length of G-rich, non-coding repeat sequences because of the double DNA sequence 5'-(TTAGGG)_n-3' observed by an end 3' G-rich single-stranded overhanging (10-15 kb in humans at childbirth) with a 150-200 nucleotide long. This overhang bends and penetrates the TTAGGG region, identical to double-stranded (10). It forms a closed telomeric loop (t-loop) that shields the 3' end of the molecule of telomeric DNA from DDR machinery, generally considering it a damaged strand that needs repair. Shelterin complex proteins are involved with telomeres and consist of three main subtypes: TRF1 and TRF2, which attach to dsDNA's diploid TTAGGG overhang, and POT1, which connects to single-stranded TTAGGG overhang (23, 24).

TIN2, TPP1, and RAP1 are three other shelterin proteins, which form a synthesized combined complex with the three cores, enable DDR monitoring systems to identify and discern the difference between telomeric and damaged genomic DNA (23). TRF2 contributes to forming the higher-order structure of the t-loop. TRF1 activities include:

- Bending of DNA to produce the t-loop.
- Enhancing telomere replication during the S stage of the cell cycle.
- Inhibiting telomerase by recruitment of TIN2 connects the TPP1- POT1 heterodimer to a single-stranded G-rich overhang (17).

TPP1 and POT1 can both favourably and adversely control telomerase activity. POT1 and TRF-2 maintain the ends against ATM and ATR-dependent DDR. RAP1 interacts with TRF-2 to strengthen its telomere-specific binding. Clinical surveys have indicated that the expression levels of shelterin genes such as TRF1, TRF2, TIN2, and POT1 are higher in tumor tissues than in non-cancerous cells. However, it has been observed that high shelterin gene expression and telomerase activity are inversely correlated with telomere length (TL). Therefore, it is probable to consider that the shelterin function as a negative regulator of telomerase (17). Shelterin protein overexpression inhibits telomerase activity, which protects short telomeres and promotes the growth of cancerous cells (**Figure 6**). Various cell subpopulations with long to short telomeres may exist throughout the cancer progression because cells with a lower length of telomeres can enhance telomerase actions to prevent a dilemma and retain their telomeres shorter when cell replication increases (25), (refer **Figure 7**).

Carol Greider, a graduate candidate, and her mentor Blackburn chose to investigate whether the synthesis of telomere DNA may be linked to an unidentified enzyme. Greider observed traces of enzymatic activity in a cell extract in 1984, from which they had extracted the enzyme telomerase, isolated it, and proved that it is made up of both RNA and protein. In humans, telomerase is dimeric and functions only as a dimer; it consists of two components: TERC and TERT. The former RNA component that contained the CCCC(A) sequence, i.e., the template for telomerase's reverse transcriptase activity, always lies within the ribonucleoprotein complex's RNA subunit (25). It acts as a draft for the telomere's development, whereas the amino component is necessary for the constructing activity, i.e., enzymatic action, refer (**Figure 8**). This complex consists of additional telomerase holoenzyme protein components within the cells that re-assemble the active enzyme and promote its function. It introduces guanine-rich repetitive sequences by reversing the 3' terminals of linear chromosomal genes with a separate proliferation process. Genomic DNA failure with each replication cycle (10). Telomerase expands genetic telomere material, creating a platform for DNA polymerase to replicate the absolute length of the chromosome without skipping the very terminal end, allowing for the repair of degenerative mutations (25).

Across the alternative side, the upregulation or overexpression of telomerase activity in cancerous/tumour cells helps to maintain telomere length and thus, propagation and the progression of cancer. The potential of replication in tumor cells could be restricted by inhibiting telomerase activity from ceasing telomere length maintenance. Since replicative senescence is an essential barrier in tumor progression, the expression of TERT is crucial in these cells. On the contrary, the expression of several telomerase holoenzyme components is purely controlled. TERC and TERT, for example, are ubiquitously expressed in unicellular eukaryotes and highly proliferative cells in humans (26).

Somatic cells that have low enzymatic activity in the telomerase action can be targeted for antitumor therapies. Studies have confirmed the presence of dyskerin, a fragmented protein necessary for telomerase functioning and the inaccurate assembly and stability of mature human Telomerase RNA (hTR). The presence of highly expressed dyskerin is observed in various tumors. The holoenzyme telomerase promotes tumorigenesis and dyskerin, i.e., closely associated with the consideration of telomeres. Antitumor therapeutics or drugs may be adequate to attack this protein.

FORK ARREST DUE TO OXIDATIVE LESIONS

The production of 8-oxoguanine seems to be the most common oxidative DNA defect in human telomeres. These oxidative damages facilitate the inhibition of the origin of replication and the initiation of the DNA damage response. Acute oxidative stress at telomeres, as per existing research, causes a decrease in TRF1 and TRF2, which have been crucial in efficient telomere replication and t-loop generation, accordingly. Additionally, a rise in γH2AX in the presence of 53BP1 implied a telomerase replication fork stall rather than a double-strand break. When the replication of telomeres was investigated using Chromosome Orientation-FISH (CO-FISH), the resulting data indicated a more significant amount of un-replicated telomeres following hydrogen peroxide treatment, validating the concept that 8-oxoG can induce replication fork stall at telomeres (27).

2-PHENYL 4H CHROMONE DERIVATIVES CONTAINING 1,3,4, OXADIAZOLE

Previous works have widely suggested that myricetin derivatives inhibit telomerase activity moderately. The insertion of amide segments into structure-activity relationships (SARs) can significantly alter the potent inhibitor of telomerase effects and cytotoxic activity. This implies that the binder present should expect to improve the inhibitory effect. It has also been found that the aromatic (benzene) ring's amount of methoxy groups influences anticancer activity (28).

Aside from this, it was known that 1,3,4-oxadiazole and the anticancer action was found in its substituted by-products and are widely applied in drug development. Based on this, an optimum design of the structure has been developed. Accordingly, 2-phenyl-4H-chromone was used it as a vital substructure, followed by the aforementioned adjustments, introducing 1,3,4-oxadiazole unsaturated added substituent and heterocycle (28), which produced a new 2-phenyl-4H-chromone analogues that showed enhanced telomerase inhibition properties. These compounds were examined to find if they had a quite a broader telomerase suppressive action as compared to myricetin and 1,3,4-oxadiazole analogues (28). The primary aim of the flow cytometric investigation would be how this medication affected cell cycle arrest, which demonstrated that this substance may cause cell cycle arrest at the G2/M phase, delaying cellular proliferation in a concentration-dependent way development and inhibiting cell proliferation (28). Cell apoptosis research indicates that these chemicals could cause apoptosis phase in a dopamine-concentration way, in line with the notion that telomerase inhibitors might cause cell death to prevent tumor cell growth (28), also (refer *Figure 9*).

PINX1 AS THE TELOMERASE INHIBITOR IN NASOPHARYNGEAL CARCINOMA

Telomerase, having an essential role in malignancy, is rightly reported in 88% of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma (NPC), with enhanced TERT expression. It has been recently found that Pin2/ TRF1 interacting protein X1 (PinX1) (26) inhibits telomerase and functions as a tumor suppressor in vivo (29). As aforementioned, dyskerin functions are critical in telomerase maintenance activities. The Western Blotting results showed that dyskerin expression significantly decreased concentration-dependent, limiting tumor development. It is a protein present in human tissues as it's slighter prominent in malignant tissues. As per the recent studies and years of research, PinX1 is often used to substantially reduce telomerase activity in gastrointestinal and liver malignant cancerous cells, causing them to undergo the apoptotic phase. Studies from other cancers like gastrointestinal and prostate suggested gene polymorphism, and PinX1 is a microtubule-binding protein that serves vital functions in telomerase inhibition, indicating that mechanisms of PinX1 regulation of telomerase inhibition may differ in different cancers. Various methods were used to detect the effects of PinX1, such as semi-quantitative RT-PCR, stretch PCR, scratch assay, MTT assay, Transwell, and flow cytometry (26). The consequences of PinX1 affecting the expression of hTERT mRNA and activation of telomerase were analyzed (29), and it was discovered that activation of PinX1 dramatically lowered hTERT mRNA level by 20.99%, reducing response of telomerase. Other effects observed were arrested mediated cellular apoptosis in NPC cell lines with G0/G1 phase. In conclusion, PinX1 is a viable telomerase inhibitor with therapeutic prospects in treating malignancies, especially NPC. Sequencing map of the gene is shown in *figure 10*.

PARP DOMAIN OF TANKYRASE 1 AS TARGET FOR CANCER THERAPY

Tankyrases enhance telomerase access to telomeres. This (TRF1 is ankyrin-related ADP-ribose polymerase one that binds with TRF2) is a 140kDa protein consisting of four characteristic domains, among which one (ANK domain) has five well-conserved subdomains. These ARCs (ANK repeat clusters I-V) work independently as a TRF-1 complex formation region (30). The identification of TRF1 by subdomains ARC V is critical for tankyrase 1's telomeric activity. The PARP region is positioned at the C-terminus of the protein, tankyrase 1 (31), also refer (Figure 11).

It stimulates the poly(ADP-ribosylation) [usually, poly(ADP-ribosylation) is involved in various biochemical functions, particularly DNA repair and replication, malignant transformation (30), and so on] of acceptor proteins (in this case, TRF1), modifying them with significant negative charges to obstruct their interactions with DNA. This suppresses TRF1's potential to bind to telomeric DNA, as it gets released from telomeres due to PARP activity and rapidly undergoes proteasomal degradation. Thus, telomere access is increased for telomerase by tankyrase one, leading to the formation of longer telomeres and eventual cancer progression. Hence, it is supposed that inhibitors of tankyrase one can be a potential target for cancer therapy, (*refer Figure 12*).

Tankyrase 1 promotes telomerase inhibitor resistance. Experiments have demonstrated that cells with overexpression of tankyrase 1, where TRF1 is produced from telomeres, and telomere length is recovered following treatment (30) with the telomerase inhibitor MST-312 (no elongation). Like 3-aminobenzamide (3-AB) and PJ-34, several known PARP inhibitors can block tankyrase 1 PARP activity and reverse this drug resistance (30). These inhibitors increase the rate of telomere lengthening and induce apoptosis crisis to arise earlier. They do not have a direct inhibitory role against telomerase activity but cause telomere shortening as through limiting telomere exposure to telomerase. Also, 3-AB doesn't immensely accelerate telomere shrinking of length in benign fibroblasts triggered by end replication defects (30), illustrating that these PARP inhibitors solely impact telomerase-positive cells. PARP inhibitors have shown little cytotoxicity when used against DNA repair-deficient cancers. The role of tankyrase 1 in mitosis (29, 30) is not much affected by PARP inhibitors, as are telomere lengths. When supplemented with other telomerase inhibitors, Tankyrase 1 is an essential potential pharmaceutical target in anti-cancer treatment (*Figure 12*).

NATURAL COMPOUNDS IN TELOMERASE INHIBITION

Various chemical compounds occurring naturally in plants (phytochemicals) can inhibit telomerase activity in multiple cancers. These are secondary metabolites, including polyphenols, alkaloids, terpenoids, xanthenes, and sesquiterpenes, and including hTERT and hTR, telomerase substrates, and binding protein which are generic primary targets (32). Allicin, a garlic-derived organophosphate, has been demonstrated to reduce telomerase activity (33) by lowering hTERT and mRNA levels and enhancing apoptosis. Curcumin, a phenol in turmeric and Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) in the tea plant, decreases telomeric activity in several cancer types by reducing mRNA and protein expression. The latter also binds competitively for the RNA substrate primer. Along with EGCG, tannic acid (TA) found in tea and other sources like red wine, grapes, beans, coffee, and nuts has been investigated to reveal impacts on telomerase enzymatic activity, cell viability and cell count in adenocarcinomas (a type of Cancer) of the breast and colon. Gingerol present in ginger, again, reduces hTERT expression and decreases c-Myc (myelocytomatosis viral oncogene). Both Gossypol from cottonseed and organosulphur derived from the family Cruciferae, Sulforaphane, cause post-translational modification of hTERT (epigenetic regulation) and phosphorylation TERT, which prevents its translocation resulting in the decrease of TERT expression. Daidzein, genistein, and others present in soybean inhibit telomerase activity and bring stabilization of G4. Hence, cancer therapy drugs can be developed by applying natural products in telomerase inhibitory roles (32).

CLINICAL TRIALS FOR USAGE OF TELOMERASE

Considering the importance of the telomerase and its implication in anti-cancer therapy. From time to time, it has been tested in various formats, either alone or in combinatorial approach that is tabulated below. The data from last few decades shows clearly that approx. 64 studies have been associated to use telomerase in several conditions. Out of many 35 has successfully completed to date. Only 3 studies have failed and 3 withdrawn to date. Data also signifies the fact that telomerase as a tool to treat major cancer types and stages have been extremely successful for all ages (**Table 1**).

TABLE 1: SUMMARIZATION OF THE VARIOUS CLINICAL TRIAL STUDIES THAT HAVE BEEN CONDUCTED TO USE IT AS EFFECTIVE METHOD TO TREAT VARIOUS CONDITIONS (34–45).

NCT Number	Conditions	Phases	URL
NCT02846103	Lung Cancer	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02846103
NCT02818426	Metastatic NSCLCr	Phase 1 Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02818426
NCT02984774	Infertility, Female	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02984774
NCT01501578	Pulmonary Fibrosis		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01501578
NCT02530255	Alzheimer Disease	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02530255
NCT04058678	Ovarian Reserve	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04058678
NCT02531334	Metabolic Syndrome X	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02531334
NCT02246738	Urothelial Carcinoma of the Bladder		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02246738
NCT01247623	Malignant Melanoma	Phase 1 Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01247623
NCT01265927	Breast Neoplasms	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01265927
NCT03591367	Bladder Cancer	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03591367
NCT03056417	Chronic Pain	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03056417
NCT02692833	Acute Kidney Injury Heart Valve Diseases Coronary Artery Disease		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02692833
NCT02060123	Abused Women	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02060123
NCT01247584	Leukemia		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01247584
NCT00069940	Brain and Central Nervous System Tumors Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumor Sarcoma	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00069940
NCT00079157	Breast Cancer	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00079157
NCT01273090	Brain and Central Nervous System Tumors Lymphoma Lymphoproliferative Disorder Small Intestine Cancer Unspecified Childhood Solid Tumor, Protocol Specific	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01273090
NCT0002116	Melanoma (Skin)	Phase	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0002116

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NCT0051013 3	Acute Myelogenous Leukemia	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0051013
NCT0451504 3	Solid Tumor, Adult	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0451504
NCT0042536 0	Pancreatic Cancer	Phase 3	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0042536
NCT0050945 7	Carcinoma, Non-Small-Cell Lung	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0050945
NCT0482326 0	Aging	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0482326
NCT0229370 7	Prostate Cancer	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0229370
NCT0195912 6	Stress Aging Well-being	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0195912
NCT0012418 9	Chronic Lymphoproliferative Diseases	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0012418
NCT0185783 0	Stress Ageing Wellbeing	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0185783
NCT0124307 3	Essential Thrombocythemia	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0124307
NCT0125676 2	Locally Recurrent or Metastatic Breast Cancer	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0125676
NCT0124293 0	Multiple Myeloma	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0124293
NCT0113796 8	Non-small Cell Lung Cancer	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0113796
NCT0199308 2	Aging Stress Disease Risk	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0199308
NCT0035363 9	Inflammatory Bowel Disease		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0035363
NCT0235582 1	Osteopenia Arterial Hypertension	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0235582
NCT0296059 4	Breast Cancer Lung Cancer Pancreatic Cancer Head and Neck Cancer Ovarian Cancer ColoRectal Cancer Gastric Cancer Esophageal Cancer HepatoCellular Carcinoma	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0296059
NCT0524310 8	Aging	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0524310
NCT0428084 8	Glioblastoma	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0428084
NCT0284005 8	Cancer	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0284005
NCT0415876 5	Male Infertility		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0415876
NCT0394635 8	Squamous Cell Carcinoma of the Head and Neck Anal Canal Cancer Cervical Cancer	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0394635
NCT0175367 4	Metabolic Syndrome Insulin Resistance	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0175367
NCT0326571 7	Leukemia, Lymphocytic, Chronic, B-Cell	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0326571
NCT0254737 6	Soft Tissue Sarcoma		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT0254737

NCT0253529 9	GLP-1 Metformin Telomere-telomerase System Par-4	Phase 4	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02535299
NCT0229924 5	Telomere Shortening Telomere Length, Mean Leukocyte 22q Telomere Deletion Syndrome	Phase 4	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02299245
NCT0155535 9	Lymphoma Multiple Myeloma		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01555359
NCT0283843 3	Melanoma	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02838433
NCT0438474 4	GH Poor Ovarian Reserve Based on POSEIDON		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04384744
NCT0157918 8	Inoperable Stage III Non-small Cell Lung Cancer	Phase 3	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01579188
NCT0092531 4	Stage IIIB Skin Melanoma Stage IIIC Skin Melanoma	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00925314
NCT0190365 5	Depressive Disorder	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01903655
NCT0319082 4	Melanoma Stage III Melanoma Stage Iv	Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03190824
NCT0169434 2	FATTY LIVER NO MALIGNANCY NO DECOMPENSATED ILLNESS		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01694342
NCT0213183 1	Cirrhosis		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02131831
NCT0212603 3	Celiac Disease	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02126033
NCT0180956 1	Endometriosis		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01809561
NCT0259256 4	Anxiety Disorders Social Anxiety Disorder	NA	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02592564
NCT0411096 4	Critical Limb Ischemia	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04110964
NCT0413364 9	Aging	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04133649
NCT0413345 4	Alzheimer Disease	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04133454
NCT0117642 2	Acute Myeloid Leukemia		https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01176422
NCT0115311 3	Metastatic Prostate Cancer	Phase 1 Phase 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01153113
NCT0156863 2	Solid Tumors Lymphoma	Phase 1	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01568632

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE CHALLENGES

Recent improvements in understanding telomere and telomerase-associated proteins and their functions through advances in technology have proved telomerase to be a potential target for anti-cancer therapy and thus inhibiting malignant progression by disrupting telomere maintenance. Anti-cancer therapies reducing the expression of hTERT or/and associated proteins can be new advances in treatment. It has been reported that oxidative stress can cause DNA lesions, especially at telomeres having high guanine content, and thus stall telomere replication, eventually causing senescence. Likewise, synthetic chemicals like myricetin derivatives, including various modifications with enhanced capabilities, have been tested successfully to retain anti-telomerase properties and induce apoptosis. According to many reports, telomerase inhibitor PinX1 can potentially treat tumors as it is expressed in normal tissues and not in tumor tissues. Ambiguous studies suggest its application to be restricted to Nasopharyngeal

Carcinoma (NPC) but not to any other cancers. These insights into the telomere and telomerase associated proteins have highlighted the interaction of tankyrase with TRF1, which promotes TL maintenance, concluding that tankyrase one can be an anti-cancer target. Apart from all these, secondary metabolites obtained from various parts of plants have shown to possess the significant anti-cancer potential for telomerase inhibition. Although telomerase might be a hard target due to a lag phase after treatment and may not be beneficial in individuals with a significant tumor burden, it can be highly effective in patients with a low tumor burden or particular oncogenic alterations. Additional research is required to determine the precise mechanisms of hTERT expression in the early phases of cancer. The molecular details regarding the escape from crisis remain unclear, while beliefs differ regarding hTERT promoter mutations. The telomerase synthesis functions holoenzyme is poorly understood. As a result, the most complicated issue is to discover the molecular complexities of telomerase's activities and then produce an inhibitor that swiftly eliminates telomerase-positive tumor cells while leaving telomerase-positive normal cells undisturbed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to Santosh Kumar, PhD (Postdoctoral Research associate, Sir Dunn School of Pathology), University of Oxford, United Kingdom for his suggestions.

FUNDING

Funding is not applicable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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TABLE AND FIGURES LEGENDS

Figure 1. Mechanism of cell division and cell ageing associated with telomere shortening: Cell cycle or division ends up with losing a portion of the segment from the end of the chromosomes that is telomere. These repetitive segments once shorten, activates the cells safeguarding mechanism that is growth arrest, senescence or apoptosis (re-sketched based on, (20, 46)).

Telomere in Cancer Cells

Figure 2. The mechanism for telomere length maintenance in cancer cells: Representation to decipher the mechanism by which telomere length remains constant throughout the time and cell divisions in cancer cells, that helps in uncontrolled proliferation and cancer progression without undergoing any apoptosis or senescence.

Figure 3. Telomere shortening and its consequences: Telomere shortening leads to loss of function followed by activation of DNA repair pathways that involves ATM and ATR, where activation of P53 leads to cell cycle arrest. In this scenario, of telomere shortening mostly cells experiences genomic instability or senescence or apoptosis as a checkpoint (34).

Figure 4. Breakage-Fusion cycle: In G1 phase, cells prepare for division, in case of any loss of segment. In G2 that is replicative phase, whole segment of chromosome is duplicated including the lost segment. This leads to bridging and fusion of two homologous chromosomes. Schematic representation of the breakage-fusion-bridge (BFB) cycle. Black circles represent the centromere of each chromosome; red circles, the telomeres (terminal telomeric repeat sequences); and green circles, the sub-telomeric region of the chromosome. IC indicates incomplete chromosome (chromatid). Arrows indicate sites where the chromosome breaks have taken place. The 'X' indicates the site of fusion. The chromatid BFB cycle is initiated when a chromosome loses a telomere (i.e. a chromosome end) due to a chromosome break leading to a terminal fragment (TF). After the chromatid break occurs, the unprotected chromosomal end is exposed and, after replication, is thought to fuse with either another broken chromatid or its sister chromatid to produce a dicentric chromosome (DIC). Due to the presence of two centromeres, the fused chromatids form a bridge during anaphase that breaks when the two centromeres are pulled to opposite poles. Since the break usually occurs in a site different from that of the fusion, one daughter cell gets a chromosome with a duplication on its end in the form of an inverted repeat, while the other gets a chromosome with a terminal deletion, which can initiate another BFB cycle unless it acquires a new telomere. Following DNA replication in the next cell cycle, the sister chromatids fuse once again and thus the cycle continues, resulting in the amplification of DNA sequences located near the telomere and at interstitial sites, as well as the progressive accumulation of terminal deletions or TFs, re-sketch version of image from the article (22).

Figure 5. Bimodal implication of telomere shortening in cancer development; (A) human somatic cells shorten their telomeres at each cell cycle. Activation of oncogenes and inactivation of tumor suppressor genes lead to dysregulated cell proliferation, which further enhances telomere shortening. A critically shortened telomere causes senescence or crisis of a cell, whereas telomere reverse transcriptase (TERT) expression mainly via promoter mutation (C228T or C250T) results in telomerase activation and tumor formation; (B) in the initial step of carcinogenesis, the level of telomerase activity (TA) is insufficient to prevent telomere shortening (TS) and indicates as “TA < TS”. Under these conditions, telomerase preferentially elongates the shortest telomeres, but the level of the enzyme activity is insufficient to maintain the bulk telomere length. After several cell cycles, additional factors upregulate telomerase activity, and the bulk telomere length is maintained short in an equilibration between TA and TS (“TA = TS”). In a tumor mass, cancer cells with short telomeres upregulate interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs), which presumably contribute to the tumor malignancy. Furthermore, shortened telomeres facilitate cancer evolution by causing moderate chromosomal instability; (C) in experimental settings, ectopic overexpression of TERT induces telomere elongation in cancer cells, which is followed by TERRA upregulation and repression of ISG expression. Because TERRA-like oligonucleotides repress ISG induction, shortened telomeres, which provide reduced TERRA levels, may be more advantageous for cancer. This figure is used as it is from the article as declared (17).

Figure 6. Telomere maintenance components. Telomeres are composed of multiple TTAGGG repeats at the end of linear chromosomes and are coated by a protein complex, shelterin, which helps maintain its integrity. Shelterin also helps recruit and modulate the telomerase complex, the enzyme responsible for telomere elongation. Telomerase has a 4-protein scaffold (dyskerin, NOP10, NHP2, and GAR) and an RNA template (TERC) and reverse transcriptase (TERT). Adapted from Townsley et al (24).

Figure 7. Mechanism of Telomere maintenance: Telomerase uses its guide RNA to base pair to the 3' end, then add bases to that end using its RNA as template, It can slide over the repeat many times, adding units of DNA, Further complementary DNA can be added resulting in lengthening of the double strand DNA (47).

Figure 8. A rendering of telomerase, showing the enzyme's various subunits (48).

Figure 9. Chemical structure of the compound: Chemical synthesis of the compound that has anti-tumor activity.

530 540 550 560 570
 TCCTCTGGAGTGGAGGGACTGGCATCGCCCTCGGGAGTCTT

Figure 10. The sequencing map of PinX1 gene (49).

Figure 11. Telomere elongation by tankyrase 1 and impact on telomerase inhibitors. For telomere elongation, active telomerase needs to gain access to the telomeric 30 -overhang. The TRF1-TIN2-TPP1-POT1 telomeric protein complex limits telomerase access, whereas tankyrase 1 removes the telomeric protein complex by poly(ADP-ribosyl)ating TRF1. Either telomere shortening or tankyrase 1 upregulation, each of which decreases the TRF1-TIN2-TPP1- POT1 loading on a chromosome end, attenuates the impact of telomerase inhibitors by allowing access of residual telomerase activity. Conversely, blockade of tankyrase 1 enhances the effect of telomerase inhibitors. The relative importance of tankyrase 1 vs tankyrase 2 inhibition remains unclear (29).

Figure 12. Structures of tankyrase 1 and tankyrase 2. HPS, homopolymeric runs of His, Pro, and Ser, without known functions; ANK, ankyrin domain, consisting of 24 ANK repeats; SAM, multimerization domain homologous to the sterile alpha motif; PARP, PARP catalytic domain that adds ADP-ribose chains onto acceptor proteins. The ANK domain is further divided into five well-conserved ANK repeat clusters (ARC), each of which contributes to ligand binding. Bridges above two adjacent ANK repeats indicate the presence of a conserved histidine contributing to inter-repeat stabilization (29).